

Night in the Woods

Developed by: Infinite Fall

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Keywords

Ethical Decision-making, Ethics, Gender Studies, Inclusion, Mental Health, Moral Development, Philosophy, Queer Studies, Religion, Trauma

Figure 1. Screenshot from *Night in the Woods* (Infinite Fall). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

Night in the Woods (NITW, see Figure 1) is a digital single-player storytelling game published by Infinite Fall in 2017 and is about college dropout Mae Borowski who returns to her economically unstable and depressing hometown of Possum Springs. Realizing that her family and friends have moved on without her, Mae tries to reconnect with her former life by wandering around town and encountering the people she left behind. Over the course of the story, players get to know the main character better and understand her intelligence, sarcasm, and self-destructive, insecure habits. Through Mae's unique perspective, the story of NITW unfolds as players explore the virtual environment and the many characters living within it, all

troubled by their own profound personal issues. Overall, the adventure game is structured with text-based dialogues and rather childlike aesthetics, but offers deep insights into its carefully constructed characters. As the game progresses, players are challenged with increasingly complex ethical decisions about sociocultural, political, and psychological issues in a gentle yet confrontational way.

Facts

Release date:	2017
Developer:	Infinite Fall
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	1
Format:	Hybrid
Time frame:	around 10 hours
Languages:	English
Environment:	access to computers/consoles
Material:	-
Price:	€20 per person

Resonance & Criticism

Since its release, NITW has been very well received and praised by the gaming community for its meaningful storytelling. Therefore, apart from being nominated in numerous other categories, the game has won several awards, including “The Game Award” for “Best Independent Game” in 2017 as well as the “SXSW Gaming Award” for “Most Fulfilling Community-Funded Game” and the “BAFTA Games Award” for “Best Narrative” in 2018 (Night in the Woods (Video Game 2017) - Awards - IMDb, n.d.). However, due to the game’s slow story development and simple game mechanics, enjoyment is not guaranteed, and some players may quickly lose interest (Trattner, 2017).

Game Principle & Process

At the start of NITW, the story is essentially the same every day: the main character wakes up, walks through town, talks to friends, and returns home to have nightmares when she sleeps. However, the repetition of Mae’s daily routines not only offers insights into her habits but also fosters players’ engagement and deepens their knowledge of the game’s characters and environments (Caravella, 2021). For this reason, the game wants players to feel as if time passes slowly at the beginning, mirroring the monotony of life in Mae’s hometown. Even her tendency toward self-destruction is built into the game’s mechanics, as players must choose between dialogue options where one seems worse than the other, showing Mae’s critical state of mind (Trattner, 2017).

Through these dialogues with the game's NPCs, NITW calls for ethical decision-making by encouraging players to reflect on their choices and rewarding them for doing so throughout the game. Furthermore, decisions are becoming increasingly complex, with less time to respond, which promotes players' ethical judgment processes (Caravella, 2021). Ultimately, playing the game creates intrinsic motivations to produce ethical arguments and cultivate the players' moral character, a relatively stable arrangement of ethical dispositions. That is why one of NITW's core game mechanisms is "affective materiality," defined as "making decisions and taking actions in a context that they are encouraged to come to care about" (Veale, 2021, p. 452). By feeling responsible for the consequences of their choices, players understand their impact on the virtual environment and the characters within it. Especially in connection with ethics, the feeling that however the story ends it will be their fault, encourages players to empathize with the characters and actively follow the game's progress.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

As a prime example of digital storytelling, the game takes a long time to develop and flesh out its characters' stories, creating compelling content and emotional depth. Therefore, whenever players are confronted with ethical decisions during the game through text-based dialogues between Mae and various citizens of Possum Springs, NITW manages to tackle rather heavy subjects without overwhelming the players. Through these conversations, players can learn about sensitive topics such as mental illness, child abuse, death, and sociopolitical issues regarding the city's state of disrepair (Trattner, 2017). Additionally, the game deals with cultural stereotypes and is a fundamentally queer experience due to the representation of several queer storylines. Moreover, since the characters are often not visually gendered, NITW promotes the fluidity of gender and sexuality, thus challenging heteronormativity as well as binary gender constructions (Trattner, 2017). By learning about various personal fates and standpoints, such as different religious views, drug addiction, and anti-capitalistic and anti-fascist arguments, the players develop their own ethical code and practice it over the course of the game.

Effectiveness

A study conducted in a classroom setting found that NITW causes players to reflect on their own moral agency and promotes their introspection, the examination of one's own conscious thoughts and feelings (Caravella, 2021). Moreover, the game can help players practice their moral decision-making and potentially adjust their ethical dispositions within and outside the virtual world. For this reason, decisions made in NITW can have lasting effects on players, given the game's complex ethical challenges (Caravella, 2021).

Furthermore, players of NITW have praised the relatability of the game's characters, especially their ability to project the fictive problems into their own lives (Veale, 2021). Accordingly, the game's creators "have spoken of being contacted by many people who had been dealing with

the same lack of medical and social support as the characters in the game” (Veale, 2021, p. 458). In conclusion, NITW can help players realize they need support and connect with others dealing with the same problems.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

As previously mentioned, NITW addresses various sensitive topics that some players may not want to deal with due to their personal backgrounds. Similarly, while some players may enjoy the slow storytelling and time-consuming character studies, others may feel trapped by the perception of responsibility, because most of the game’s stories are burdening experiences. Therefore, players might feel alienated because they cannot change things for the better, and most characters’ fates are predetermined, which is more likely to be categorized as unfavorable.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

Sources

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